

GEOMETRIYADAN OLIMPIADA MASALALARINI YECHISH USULLARI

Rasulova Gulnozaxon Azamovna^{1, 2}Mamadaliyeva Durdona Aminjon qizi

¹Dotsent, Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qo'qon davlat pedagogika instituti, Matematika kafedrası,

²Qo'qon davlat pedagogika instituti 1-bosqich talabasi

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Anotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada matematika fan olimpiadasi masalalari yechimlarini aniqlashda vujudga keladigan qiyinchiliklar va ularni bartaraf qilishga doir masalalar yechib ko'rsatilgan. Ba'zi geometrik masalalarni turlicha usullarda yechish yoritilgan bo'lib, olimpiada masalalarini yechish o'quvchilarning fikrlash doiralari nafaqat kengayadi, balki izlanuvchanlik, kreativlik qobiliyatlari shakllanadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: kvadrat, mediana, soha yuzi, aylana, uchburchak balandliklari, perpendikulyar, uchburchakka ichki va tashqi chizilgan aylanalar, parallellogramm yuzi.

Ta'lim tizimini rivojlangan mamlakatlar darajasiga olib chiqish va shu orqali mamlakatimizda matematika ta'limi samaradorligini oshirishga erishish eng dolzarb muammolardan biriga aylanib qoldi. Bizga ma'limki, maktab, AL, KHK o'quvchilari hamda OTM talabalari o'rtasida har yili fan olimpiadalari, shu jumladan, matematika fan olimpiadasi ham o'tkaziladi. Olimpiada ishtirokchilarining ijodiy faolligini o'strishda, tafakkur jarayonini shakllantrishda mantiqiy fikrlash hamda matematikadan murakkab, nostandart masalalarni yechish alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Olimpiada masalalarini yechish o'quvchidan chuqur va mustahkam bilim talab etadi. Bunday bilimni egallash uchun har bir o'quvchi darsliklar bilan cheklanib qolmasdan qo'shimcha adabiyotlardan ham foydalanishi, mantiqiy fikrlashni oshirishi zarur.

Ushbu maqolada matematika fan olimpiadasi masalalari yechimlarini aniqlashda vujudga keladigan qiyinchiliklar va ularni bartaraf qilishga doir masalalar yechib ko'rsatilgan.

1-masala. Uchburchakka ichki chizilgan aylana radiusi 15 ga teng. Bu radius uchburchakning bir tomonini 26 va 25 ga teng bo'lgan kesmalarga ajratadi. Uchburchakning qolgan tomonlari uzunliklarini toping.

$$AB = ? \quad AC = ? \quad r = 15$$

$$r = \frac{2S}{a+b+c}$$

$$p = \frac{x+26+51+x+25}{2} = x+51$$

$$S = \sqrt{(x+51) \cdot 25 \cdot 26 \cdot x} - \text{Geron}$$

$$15 = \frac{2 \cdot \sqrt{(x+51) \cdot 25 \cdot 26 \cdot x}}{2x+102}$$

$$15(x+51) = \sqrt{(x+51) \cdot 25 \cdot 26 \cdot x}$$

1-chizma.

$$3(x+51) = \sqrt{(x+51) \cdot 26 \cdot x}$$

$$9(x+51)^2 = (x+51) \cdot 26 \cdot x$$

$$9(x+51) = 26x \quad 17x = 459 \quad x = 27$$

$$AB = 26 + x = 53 \quad AC = 25 + x = 52$$

Javob: $AB = 53, AC = 52$

2-masala. Teng yonli to'g'ri burchakli uchburchak gipotenuzasi 45 ga teng. Unga to'g'ri to'rtburchak shunday ichki chizilganki, to'g'ri to'rtburchakning ikki uchi uchburchak gipotenuzasida qolgan ikki uchi katetlarda yotadi. Agar to'g'ri to'rtburchak tomonlari 5:2 nisbatda bo'lsa, uning perimetrini toping.

Bu masalani 2 xil xolatda ishlash mumkin.

1-hol. $C = 45$, 5:2 nisbat

$$2x + 5x + 2x = 45$$

$$9x = 45$$

$$x = 5$$

$$5x = 5 \cdot 5 = 25$$

$$2x = 2 \cdot 5 = 10$$

$$P = 2 \cdot (25 + 10) = 70$$

Javob: $P = 70$

2-hol.

$c = 45$, 5:2 nisbat

$$5x + 2x + 5x = 45$$

$$12x = 45$$

$$x = \frac{15}{4} = 3,75$$

$$P = 2 \cdot (5x + 2x) = 14x = 14 \cdot \frac{15}{4} = 7 \cdot \frac{15}{2} = 52,5$$

Javob: $P = 52,5$

3-masala. $\angle CAH + \angle FAH + \angle GAH = ?$

Berilgan 4-chizma bo'yicha

masalani yeching.

Bu masalalarni ham 2 xil holatda ishlash mumkin.

4-chizma.

1-hol. ABCD kvadrat uchun AC diagonal vazifasida kelyapti. Demak, $\angle CAH = 45^\circ$.

$$\angle FAE \Rightarrow \operatorname{tg} \alpha = \frac{x}{2x} = \frac{1}{2}, \quad \alpha = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\angle GAH = \beta \Rightarrow \operatorname{tg} \beta = \frac{x}{3x} = \frac{1}{3}, \quad \beta = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1}{3}$$

$$\angle FAE = \angle FAH$$

$$\alpha + \beta = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1}{2} + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1}{3}$$

5-chizma.

$$\operatorname{tg}(\alpha + \beta) = \operatorname{tg}\left(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{1}{2} + \operatorname{arctg} \frac{1}{3}\right) = \frac{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{1}{3}}$$

$$\operatorname{tg}(\alpha + \beta) = 1$$

$$\alpha + \beta = 45^\circ$$

$$\begin{cases} \angle CAH = 45^\circ \\ \angle FAH + \angle GAH = 45^\circ \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \angle GAH + \angle FAH + \angle GAH = \\ = 45^\circ + 45^\circ = 90^\circ \end{cases}$$

2-hol. Bu masalani 2-holda ishlash uchun berilgan shaklga simmetrik qilib shakl chizib olamiz.

$$\angle GAH = \alpha, \quad \angle FAH = \alpha + \beta$$

$$2\alpha + \beta = 45^\circ$$

$$AF = \sqrt{x^2 + (2x)^2} = \sqrt{5}x$$

$$\begin{cases} \angle CAH = 45^\circ \\ \angle FAH = \alpha + \beta \\ \angle GAH = \alpha \end{cases}$$

$$FK = \sqrt{x^2 + (2x)^2} = \sqrt{5}x$$

6-chizma.

$$\begin{aligned} \angle CAH + \angle FAH + \angle GAH &= \\ &= 45^\circ + 2\alpha + \beta = 45^\circ + 45^\circ = 90^\circ. \end{aligned}$$

$$AK = \sqrt{x^2 + (3x)^2} = \sqrt{10}x$$

$$AF^2 + FK^2 = AK^2$$

Demak, AFK uchburchak to'g'ri burchakli uchburchakdir. (Teng yonli ham).

4-masala. Muntazam uchburchak ichidan olingan nuqtadan uchburchak uchlarigacha bo'lgan masofalar 3,4,5 bo'lsa, uchburchak tomonini toping.

Bu masalani ishlashda ixtiyoriy uchburchak chizib olamiz va uni har bir tomoni bo'yicha simmetrik ko'rsatamiz.

$$ABC \text{ mustazam uchburchak } \alpha + \beta = 60^\circ.$$

$$\text{Demak, } \angle EBK = 120^\circ.$$

$$EK = x \text{ deb olib } \cos. \text{lar}$$

teoremasini qo'llaymiz.

$$x^2 = 4^2 + 4^2 - 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 4 \cdot \cos 120^\circ$$

$$x = 4\sqrt{3}.$$

7-chizma.

KCL va EAL uchburchaklar ham teng yonli uchburchak va uchidagi burchagi 120° bo'lgani uchun $EL = 3\sqrt{3}$ va $KL = 5\sqrt{3}$ ga teng.

Demak, KEL uchburchak to'g'ri burchali uchburchak.

$$\text{Ma'lumki, } \angle BEA = 150^\circ.$$

Uchburchak AEB uchburchak uchun $\cos. \text{lar}$ teoremasini qo'llaymiz.

$$AB^2 = AE^2 + EB^2 - 2AE \cdot EB \cos 150^\circ$$

$$AB^2 = 25 + 2\sqrt{3}$$

$$AB = \sqrt{25 + 12\sqrt{3}}$$

$$\text{Javob: } AB = BC = AC = \sqrt{25 + 12\sqrt{3}}$$

5-masala. Berilgan 8-chizma bo'yicha masalani yeching.

$$S_{BDEC} = 8, \quad S_{ABC} = ?$$

$$AB = 7, \quad AD = 4$$

$$AC = 8, \quad AE = 6$$

$$1\text{-hol. } \begin{cases} S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \sin \alpha \\ S_{ADE} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \sin \alpha \end{cases}$$

$$S_{ABC} - S_{ADE} = 2 \sin \alpha - 12 \sin \alpha$$

$$8 = 16 \sin \alpha$$

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow S_{ABC} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \cdot \frac{1}{2} = 14$$

Javob: 14

$$2\text{-hol. } \frac{S_{ABC}}{S_{ADE}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot 7 \cdot 8 \sin \alpha}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot 4 \cdot 6 \sin \alpha} = \frac{7}{3}$$

$$S_{ABC} = 7S, \quad S_{ADE} = 3S$$

$$7S - 3S = S_{BDEC}$$

$$4S = 8$$

$$S = 2$$

$$S_{ABC} = 7S = 7 \cdot 2 = 14$$

Javob: 14

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, mazkur maqola maktab, AL, KHK o'quvchilari hamda OTM talabalari o'rtasidagi matematika fan olimpiadasiga tayyorgarlik ko'ruvchilar uchun mo'ljallangan bo'lsada, undan matematikadagi bilimlarini yanada chuqurlashtirish va mustahkamlashtirmoqchi bo'lgan har bir qiziquvchi o'quvchi va talabalar foydalanishi mumkin.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. B.K.Kamolov, N.B.Kamalov "Matematikadan bilimlar bellashuvi va olimpiada masalalari", -Urganch: "Quvanchbek-Mashxura" MCHJ nasriyoti, 2018. 341- bet.
2. M.A.Mirzahmedov, D.Sotvoldiyev. "O'quvchilarni matematik olimpiadalarga tayyorlash". Toshkent "O'qituvchi" 1993 yil.
3. H.Norjigitov, A.X.Nuraliyev "Matematikadan olimpiada masalalari", Toskent, 2020. 243-bet

4. B.A.Shoimqulov, R.M.Madrahimov, N.B.Kamalov “Talabalarning matematikadan olimpiada masalalari”.
5. Titu Andreescu, Dorin Andrica “An Introduction to Diophantine Equation”. Romania “GIL Publishing House” 2002.